

Effect of split N application on grain yield, panicle numbers, and filled grains and unfilled grains of rice.^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

N application					Grain yield (t/ha)			Panicles/m ² (no.)			Filled grains/panicle (no.)			Unfilled grains (%)		
Basal	Tillering	6-7 DBPI ^b	Boot	Heading	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean
1/2	1/4	1/4	–	–	6.2	6.8	6.5	184	183	184	136	132	134	11	17	14
2/3	–	1/3	–	–	6.5	6.8	6.7	182	193	188	126	125	126	20	19	20
1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5	6.9	7.9	7.4	183	197	190	147	132	140	08	12	10
1/4	1/4	1/6	1/6	1/6	6.9	7.4	7.2	191	188	190	141	134	138	10	10	10
Mean					6.6	7.2		185	190		138	131		12	15	
Treatment					LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)		
N rate					0.4			ns			ns			ns		
Time of N application					0.5			ns			ns			4		
Interaction																
N rate at same or different time of application					ns			ns			ns			ns		
Time of N application within a N rate					ns			ns			ns			ns		
CV (%) based on error b					7			7			7			28		

^ans = nonsignificant. ^bDays before panicle initiation.

Response to N application time was significant (see table). Applying N 1/5 or 1/4 as basal and 1/5 or 1/6 N

topdressed 1 wk before panicle initiation, booting, and heading increased grain yield 10%. The increase

in yield was primarily due to more filled grains per panicle. □

Effect of single superphosphate and granular superphosphate fertilizer on rice yield

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We compared response of rice to single superphosphate (SSP) (16% water soluble and 2% citric soluble P₂O₅) and granular superphosphate (GSP) (14.8% water soluble and 3.6% citric soluble P₂O₅) during 1987 wet season.

Medium-duration cultivar Kranti was transplanted 20 Jul 1987 and harvested 4 Nov 1987. Soil was medium heavy (sandy loam) with pH 6.7, 0.42% organic C, CEC 32.6 mg/100 g, and 210 kg available N, 10.5 kg available P, and 325 kg available K/ha. All treatments received 60-40-20 kg NPK/ha except that the control plot received no P. N was applied in three splits: 50% basal, 25% topdressed at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

For both SSP and GSP, treatments were all P as basal, all P at tillering, and

Effect of P source on rice yield and yield attributing characters. Raipur, India, 1988.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)
Control (no P)	2.9	3.6	3.8	14.1
GSP at transplanting	3.9	4.8	4.0	15.0
SSP at transplanting	4.8	5.9	5.6	16.2
GSP at tillering	3.7	4.6	4.0	14.3
SSP at tillering	4.3	5.2	5.0	15.8
GSP: 50% at transplanting, 50% at tillering	4.1	5.1	5.0	15.1
SSP: 50% at transplanting, 50% at tillering	5.3	6.4	5.8	17.1
LSD (0.05)	0.8	0.8	ns	

split P, 50% at transplanting and 50% at tillering.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Plot size was 144 m²; plant spacing was 20 × 20 cm.

Reduction of rice yield without any P fertilization was significant (see table). Applied as basal, SSP was much superior to GSP. Yield was significantly higher with SSP split application.

The relatively higher availability of P in water-soluble SSP might have made the difference under wetland conditions. □

Performance of *Sesbania rostrata* in acid soils

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We compared *S. rostrata*, a newly introduced green manure crop, with *S. aculeata* and *Crotalaria juncea*, green manure crops commonly grown in Kerala.